

ANALYSIS OF THE SITUATION AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF SMALL BUSINESS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This article is aimed at determining the development trend of the small business sector in the economy during the period of independence of the country, and based on the determination and analysis of the situation of this sector in the cross-section of economic sectors, the factors that motivate the further development of the sector have been identified. As a research object, small business entities of the Samarkand region were selected, its general situation was analyzed, territorial characteristics were determined, and as a result of comparative analysis with small business entities operating in the sector of the republic's economic sectors, in the implementation of the goals of rapid development of the industry, its state and growth trend. Scientifically important conclusions are presented to determine the motivating factors.*

Keywords: *small business, digital economy, government support, development trend, gross domestic product.*

INTRODUCTION

After independence, one of the main tasks of the conducted research is to study and analyze the state and development trends of small business, which has become a pillar of the national economy for more than thirty years of its development. Therefore, in the process of researching the stages of development of small business, which is the first stage of entrepreneurship in the country, we considered it appropriate to mention the scientific research carried out in this direction.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

Dissertation work of U.V.Gafurov, one of the local research scientists issues related to encouraging the state's entrepreneurial activity and creating a favorable environment for it were researched, and in his research, he identified five stages of development (stage I - 1992-1995; stage II - 1995-1998; stage III - 1998-2003; stage IV - 2003-2011; Stage V - from 2011 to the present) has been gradually improved.

Analyzing the periods of the development of small business entities after independence, it became clear from the above research that its growth rates have been improved on the basis of economic reforms since the mentioned stages until now. In this regard, a number of laws and by-laws aimed at further development of the field are cited in the section of the dissertation entitled "The system of regulatory and support measures for the improvement of small business management" (pages 55-56).

The prospects of achieving social, political and economic stability, which are among the three main tasks facing the new Uzbekistan, are directly related to the state and development trends of this sector. After all, "90 percent of the jobs created in our country every year are contributed by the private sector". This indicates that in the conditions of the current globalization and the formation of the digital economy, drastic measures should be taken to improve the competitiveness of small businesses in the world market, based on the creation of comprehensive conditions for the full implementation of their innovative potential, the extension of the life cycle of small business activities .

The third section of the new edition of the Constitution adopted this year, that is, the twelfth chapter entitled "Economic Foundations of Society" Articles 65, 66, and 67 also strengthen the guarantees of entrepreneurial status, inviolability and freedom of activity. It was also noted that the state provides a favorable investment and business environment.

As a result of the economic, political and social reforms carried out by the state, the share of small business entities in the economy grew at a high rate. We believe that identifying the potential trends of small business, analyzing its general situation and determining regional characteristics is the main task of our ongoing research work.

RESULTS

Based on the analysis of small business statistics, it allowed to assess how it has changed over the years and identify development trends. In order to have a more complete picture of the development of the industry in the country, it is appropriate to focus on its dynamics over the period selected for the study, that is, from 2013 to 2023 (Figure 1).

The total number of small business entities in the republic's regions increased by 33.9% in 2023 compared to 2013, or almost 3 times, and their main growth trend began in 2019 and increased by 2 times (50.2%) in 2023 compared to 2019. In this five-year period (2019-2023), the total number of enterprises and organizations increased by 1.8 times (54.6 percent) has increased. From 2013 to the present day, this indicator was 2.6 times (38.7 percent).

Figure 1. The trend of development from 2013 to 2023 of the comparative analysis of the total number of enterprises, organizations and the total number of small business entities operating in the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan¹

According to the results of the comparative analysis, the total number of enterprises and organizations differed by 77.5 percent (1.3 times) compared to the total number of small business entities in 2013, and by 2023 it was 88.4 percent (1.1 times). From this, it can be concluded that the main part of the total share of enterprises and organizations corresponds to the contribution of small business entities, and it was determined that the dynamics of their development began in

¹ ЎзР Президенти ҳузуридаги статистика агентлиги расмий сайти маълумотлари асосида муаллиф томонидан тузилди

2019, which is the absolute maximum indicator of the dynamic development trend in the last ten years.

So, during the years 2013-2022, the number of business entities operating in the small business sector in Uzbekistan increased at a much faster rate than in other sectors of the national economy. As a result, the share of the number of enterprises in this sector increased in 2013 compared to 2022, that is, it increased by 10.9 points. As a result of these analyses, rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship by the state in Uzbekistan, its share in GDP it is possible to conclude that the macroeconomic policy, which is being carried out in order to increase and make employment a leading factor in ensuring the employment of the population, is giving its practical results.

In the process of researching the state of the small business sector on a national scale, it is appropriate to analyze the indicators of its regional distribution, that is, regional development trends. In the process of studying statistical data, the share of small business entities operating in the region in relation to the total number of enterprises and organizations was determined, and their ten-year development trend was analyzed (table 1).

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1-Table

The share of small business entities operating in the cross-section of regions in relation to the number of enterprises and organizations operating in the cross-section of regions²
(From 2013 to 2023, excluding farmers and farms)

Regions	The number of enterprises and organizations operating in the region (without farmers and farms)										
	Years										
	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023
Republic of Karakalpakstan	1127 4	1130 6	1223 4	1255 2	1294 6	1374 2	1559 0	1840 4	2196 8	2372 1	2669 2
Andijan	2260 6	2399 1	2483 5	2604 8	2627 8	2464 4	2739 1	3074 0	3672 6	4047 4	4465 8
Bukhara	1240 3	1146 8	1208 2	1382 8	1480 9	1562 5	1811 5	2345 9	2823 3	3116 0	3368 6
Jizzakh	9053	9414	9722	1007 6	1069 4	1200 8	1422 6	1719 0	2099 3	2271 4	2584 7

² ЎзР Президенти ҳузуридаги статистика агентлиги расмий сайти маълумотлари асосида муаллиф томонидан тузилди

Kashkadar ya	2043 7	1986 8	1957 0	1855 7	1800 5	1847 1	2091 5	2525 9	3018 0	3616 8	4161 2
Navoiy	7919	8062	8127	8533	8771	9469	1117 5	1706 7	2013 3	2271 1	2517 9
Namangan	1507 6	1595 3	1669 8	1769 5	1874 6	1995 2	2126 9	2590 9	3088 2	3342 2	3691 4
Samarkan d	1649 7	1740 3	1761 0	1855 3	1943 5	2106 1	2506 6	3135 4	3894 6	4666 7	5416 3
Surkhanda rya	1164 9	1403 6	1225 9	1220 7	1300 3	1371 9	1517 2	1922 0	2536 7	2829 1	3142 7
Sirdarya	7423	7952	8195	8300	8993	9392	1036 7	1316 9	1542 5	1592 0	1725 9
Tashkent	2133 3	2282 3	2395 4	2440 3	2501 9	2691 9	3103 0	3852 3	4617 3	5029 6	5547 2
Ferghana	1923 0	2117 3	2179 5	2308 3	2331 0	2557 1	2912 8	3537 9	4224 1	4662 2	5274 6
Khorezm	1204 3	1250 2	1300 3	1289 9	1334 2	1367 4	1483 7	1861 4	2197 9	2516 0	2890 4
Tashkent city	4223 4	4525 0	4660 3	5102 4	5507 7	6128 4	6923 6	8384 6	9595 1	1056 03	1178 12
The number of small business entities operating in the region (without farmers and farms)											
Republic of Karakalpa kstan	8264	8383	9327	9642	9638	1053 9	1198 5	1467 7	1828 8	1999 8	2286 3
Andijan	1864 5	1996 6	2087 2	2198 2	2171 3	2034 2	2256 0	2580 7	3168 3	3499 9	3903 8
Bukhara	9697	8724	9386	1114 1	1161 5	1264 8	1480 5	1998 1	2480 9	2769 0	3008 2
Jizzakh	6797	7183	7505	7881	8013	9310	1119 7	1401 1	1772 5	1946 3	2247 4
Kashkadar ya	1668 6	1608 7	1580 8	1487 0	1378 5	1434 7	1621 8	2030 4	2529 7	3115 2	3642 1
Navoiy	6047	6219	6309	6728	6731	7569	9104	1488 5	1791 3	2047 2	2284 4
Namangan	1143 5	1229 2	1308 0	1409 4	1466 7	1594 9	1697 5	2146 1	2653 1	2894 9	3230 5
Samarkan d	1111 7	1264 8	1286 0	1384 0	1398 1	1600 5	1962 9	2564 3	3311 4	4072 4	4794 3
Surkhanda rya	8195	1059 0	9062	9061	9418	1040 9	1161 8	1550 9	2156 3	2439 5	2736 8
Sirdarya	5674	6143	6403	6499	6954	7462	8318	1102 6	1336 0	1380 8	1503 6

Tashkent	1643 8	1784 8	1900 9	1954 6	1945 8	2164 7	2541 0	3260 2	4022 3	4415 6	4914 5
Ferghana	1418 3	1611 3	1692 0	1810 8	1780 2	2022 5	2330 4	2930 0	3611 7	4040 3	4635 0
Khorezm	9535	9911	1039 3	1029 8	1038 4	1090 0	1181 5	1545 3	1887 5	2198 4	2561 6
Tashkent city	3483 4	3776 0	3908 0	4341 4	4643 5	5231 4	5999 2	7410 8	8568 7	9464 1	1060 71
Share of the number of enterprises and organizations operating in the cross-section of regions, in the number of enterprises and organizations operating in the cross-section of regions (in percent)											
Republic of Karakalpakstan	73,3	74,1	76,2	76,8	74,4	76,7	76,9	79,7	83,2	84,3	85,6
Andijan	82,5	83,3	84,0	84,4	82,6	82,5	82,4	83,9	86,3	86,5	87,4
Bukhara	78,2	76,1	77,7	80,6	78,4	80,9	81,7	85,2	87,9	88,9	89,3
Jizzakh	75,0	76,3	77,2	78,2	74,9	77,5	78,7	81,5	84,3	85,7	86,9
Kashkadarya	81,6	80,9	80,8	80,1	76,6	77,7	77,5	80,4	83,8	86,1	87,5
Navoiy	76,4	77,1	77,6	78,8	76,7	79,9	81,5	87,2	88,9	90,1	90,7
Namangan	75,8	77,0	78,3	79,6	78,2	79,9	79,8	82,8	85,9	86,6	87,5
Samarkand	67,4	72,7	73,0	74,6	71,9	75,9	78,3	81,8	85,0	87,3	88,5
Surkhandarya	70,3	75,4	73,9	74,2	72,4	75,9	76,6	80,7	85,0	86,2	87,0
Sirdarya	76,4	77,2	78,1	78,3	77,3	79,4	80,2	83,7	86,6	86,7	87,1
Tashkent	77,0	78,2	79,3	80,1	77,8	80,4	81,9	84,6	87,1	87,8	88,6
Ferghana	73,7	76,1	70,6	74,2	71,1	75,1	75,1	76,0	85,5	86,7	87,9
Khorezm	79,1	79,3	79,9	79,8	77,8	79,7	79,6	83,0	85,9	87,4	88,6
Tashkent city	82,5	83,4	83,8	85,1	84,3	85,4	86,6	88,4	89,3	89,6	90,0

The analysis of this table shows that the highest indicators of the number of small business entities by region in 2023 are firstly, the city of Tashkent 106,071 (3 times in 2023 with a difference of 32.8% compared to 2013), Tashkent 49,145 (in 2023 compared to 2013 33 2.9 times with a difference of 4%, followed by Samarkand 47943 (in 2023 with a difference of 23.2% compared to 2013 by 4.3 times), Fergana 46350 (in 2023 compared to 2013 by 30.6% to 3.3 times), Andijan to 39,038 (2.1 times in 2023 with a 47.8% difference compared to 2013), Kashkadarya to 36,421 (2.2 times in 2023 with a 45.8% difference compared to 2013) ha, Namangan is equal to 32305 (2.8 times in 2023 with a difference of 35.4% compared to 2013), these provinces are leading.

Growth rates include low-valued plots as of 2023, Khorezm to 25,616 (2.7 times in 2023 with a 37.2% difference compared to 2013), Namangan to 22,844 (in 2023 with a 35.4% difference compared to 2013). 8 times), Jizzakh to 22,474 (in 2023 with a 30.2% difference compared to 2013 by 3.3 times) and the lowest indicator is Syrdaryo 15036 (in 2023 by 37.7% compared to 2013 by 2.6 times) corresponded to The analysis revealed that although the growth rates of these regions in 2023 were underestimated, a positive trend was observed in their ten-year development interval.

From the analysis of the general data of the table, it became clear that the highest indicator of the number of small business entities in the region corresponds to the city of Tashkent (in 2023, its share compared to the Samarkand region is more than 2.2 times), in the development trend from 2013 to 2023, the Samarkand region is the highest compared to all regions. A leading indicator was recorded with a growth rate of 4.3 times.

Between 2013 and 2023, the majority of the difference between the number of small business entities operating in the region and the total number of enterprises and organizations operating in the region was initially 21.1 points in Samarkand, 16.7 points in Surkhandarya, 14.3 points in Navoi, and 14.2 points in Ferghana. , by 12.3 points in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, by 11.9 points in Jizzakh, by 11.7 points in Namangan, by 11.6 points in Tashkent, by 11.1 points in Bukhara, by 10.7 points in Syrdarya, by 9.5 points in Khorezm, by 7.5 points in the city of Tashkent , it was found that it increased by 5.9 points in Kashkadarya and 4.9 points in Andijan. Therefore, according to the analysis made according to Table 1, in the period selected for the study, the Samarkand region recorded leadership indicators compared to the rest of the regions in terms of the development trend of small business entities.

The result of the above analysis shows that under the essence of small business development, practical proof of economic reforms can be seen in the development of our country's economy, creation of new jobs, business environment and reliable legal guarantees.

On the basis of the positive growth trend of the indicators of the small business sector in the regions of the region, it was determined that it was formed on the basis of the attention given to this sector from the first years of the economic policy of our state, i.e., the development of the legislation and legal framework, measures aimed at increasing the role of the financial support system and market infrastructures. .

As we observe the tendency of the small business sector to grow from year to year in the country's economy, it is important to determine the factors that motivate the further development of the sector based on the determination and analysis of its situation in the sector of the economy. Since the small business entities of the Samarkand region were selected as the research object, comparative analyzes were made with the small business entities operating in the sector of the republic's economic sectors (Fig. 2).

This diagram is analyzed by ten-year indicators, and the rate of quantitative growth of small business entities compared to the sectors of the republic's economy, the largest share of them in 2023 compared to 2014 is in accommodation and catering services by 6.3 points, in trade by 3.7 points, in industry by 2 point and increased by 2.1 points in information and communication. From the results of the analysis, it became clear that in the last ten years, the share of indicators of small business entities of the region in the economic sectors of the republic, in the first years of the selected period, the industry and trade sectors had a predominance, and in recent years, they have made a higher share in the services of living and food, and again in the trade sectors.

Figure 2. The share of the main indicators of small business and private entrepreneurship in the economic sectors of the Samarkand region (in billion soums) in the total economic sectors of the republic (%)³

CONCLUSION

From this, it can be concluded that the trade network has returned to a favorable position in the ten-year development trend of the above-mentioned economic sectors. Also, while the share of small business entities in the field of information and communication in the sector of the region's economy shows a position of development in the ten-year interval, its share remains at a very low level compared to the rest of the sectors.

The results of the above analysis made it possible to determine the factors driving the growth trend of the small business in the implementation of the goals of its rapid development.

First, on the basis of implementing measures to further increase the number of small business entities in the sector of the economy, to achieve attractiveness in its size.

Secondly, to take into account the aspects that cause the qualitative changes in the state of certain sectors that are developing with a positive trend in the field to be taken into account.

Thirdly, to develop the contribution of the digital economy in the country, based on the elimination of systemic problems in the information and communication network, which has a very low indicator at the level of the republic and Samarkand region.

Fourthly, to increase the share of electronic trade in the country by adapting the trade network, which recorded high indicators in terms of the number, volume and growth trend of all sectors, to the trend of the digital economy.

In short, it is necessary to implement measures aimed at the wider formation of the competitive environment in small business and private entrepreneurship, taking into account the current situation. In this regard, along with the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in all sectors of the economy, it is appropriate to pay special attention to small business entities that are less developed in terms of quantity.

³ ЎзР Президенти ҳузуридаги статистика агентлиги расмий сайти маълумотлари асосида муаллиф томонидан тузилди

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